

Effects of Titanate Coupling Agents on the Mechanical Properties of Poly(Vinyl Chloride)-Glass Flake Composites

K. Tanaka

Government Industrial Research Institute, Osaka, Midorigaoka 1, Ikeda City, Osaka 563, Japan

ABSTRACT

Plates were prepared with poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC) filled with glass flakes (GF) in the range of 0-70 vol% and coupling agents. The volume fraction of voids increased abruptly at 0.5-0.6 of the volume fraction of GF (Φ_f), after that Φ_f reached constant values, 0.57- 0.68 for the systems. They are the maximum packing values. Dynamic mechanical properties of the composites were measured over the temperature range from room temperature to about 120°C. The relative moduli (E_r') for the composites were less than 2.4 in glassy state. They were lower than the value estimated from Wu's equation and near that estimated from the modified Halpin-Tsai's equation at about $\Phi_f=0.2$. An evaluation of E_r' of the composites was made by using a different value of the modulus of GF agreeing with the experimental data. It was assumed that the effect of treatment with titanate coupling agents was superior to that with silane coupling agents by playing a role as plasticizer to PVC.

INTRODUCTION

Mechanical properties of the composites filled with particulate fillers are influenced by concentration, shape, orientation, and dispersion of the fillers, and reactivity and wettability of the fillers with matrix. Influence of voids in the composites, especially highly filled, also should not be neglected, as pointed out by Price et. al. (1).

In order to investigate these factors, the composites consisting of poly-(vinyl chloride) latex which can be mixed fillers until 80 vol% concentration and glass powders which can give many filler shapes as ground, lod, sphere, and disk have been used. It was reported that the modulus of composite increases when the orientation of glass flakes is good and, in highly filled composites, the glass flakes are treated with silane coupling agents (2-3).

The purpose of the present work is to investigate the effect of titanate coupling agents on the mechanical properties of composites filled with glass flakes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Poly(vinyl chloride) latex (PVC) (Nipol 531, Nippon Zeon Co.) was used as the matrix polymer, Commercial glass flakes (GF) (E-glass type, Nippon Glass Fiber Co.) having the particle size range of about 4 μm in thickness and 251-297 μm in width were used as the filler after the surfaces were washed with benzene and acetone, successively. Three titanate coupling agents (Kenrich Petrochemicals Inc.) and a silane coupling agent (Shin-Etsu Chemical Co.) were used, as listed in Table 1.

The composites were prepared by mixing 0-70 vol% of fillers with PVC latex. The coupling agents were added to the mixtures by 0.5 wt% of PVC and GF. The mixtures were shaped to plates using wood-made mould and dried at 40°C under reduced pressure. After displacing the crude plates into a metal mould and heating to 150-170°C, they were moulded for 30 min at the same temperature and under 200 kg/cm^2 pressure, as described the previous paper (2). Table 2 lists concentration of GF in samples. Attempts of making the plates from the composites of GF concentration of 70 vol% for series UT, TB, and TT, and 80 vol% for series TA and SA failed because they were too fragile to machine. For test specimens, the plates were machined to the size of 0.5 X 0.5 X 8 cm, and annealed 24 hr at 60°C. The concentration of the GF in the composites were determined from the residue of the specimens burned at 700°C for 30 min in air. Apparent densities of the specimens were obtained by measuring the size and weight, and observed densities were obtained at 25°C by pycnometry.

Dynamic mechanical properties were measured over the temperature range from room temperature to about 120°C at a frequency of 110 Hz by the Rheovibron DDV-III-ATP (Toyo Baldwin Co.). Arrangements of GF particles in the specimens were observed by the scanning electric microscope (SEM, Hitachi Co.). Reactivities of the titanate and silane coupling agents with PVC and GF were estimated by the measurements of DSC and FTIR.

Table 1
Titanate and silane coupling agent

Code	Chemical structure
TB	Tetraisopropyl di(dioctylphosphite) titanate (KR-46B)
TT	Titanium di(dioctylpyrophosphate) oxyacetate + Ethylene diamine (2:1) (KR-138T)
TA	Isopropyl tri(N-aminoethyl-aminoethyl) titanate (KR-44)
SA	N-(6 -Aminoethyl)- 8 -aminopropyl trimethoxy silane (KBM-603)

Table 2
Concentration of glass flake and treatment
with coupling agents in the samples

Sample code	X	Concentration of GF (vol%)	Coupling agent
UT-X	0, 2, 4, 5, and 6	0, 20, 40, 50, and 60	--
TB-X	0, 2, 4, and 5	0, 20, 40, and 50	TB
TT-X	0, 2, 3, 5, and 6	0, 20, 30, 50, and 60	TT
TA-X	0, 2, 4, 5, and 7	0, 20, 40, 50, and 70	TA
SA-X	0, 2, 4, 5, and 7	0, 20, 40, 50, and 70	SA

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Properties of the plate samples

There are more and less voids arounds GF particles in the plates. Figure 1 shows the apparent and observed densities of the plate samples for series UT, TT, and TA. While the apparent density decreases abruptly at about 50-60 vol% of GF, decrease of observed density of highly filled specimens is relatively small. This phenomenon shows that most of the voids are continuous one another in the specimens highly filled.

Figure 2 shows the relation of volume fraction of PVC (Φ_m), GF (Φ_f), and voids (Φ_v) for series UT, TT, and TA. Φ_f increases linearly as the concentration of GF increases in the range of 0-0.4, and Φ_v is maintained less than 0.015. The Φ_v increases abruptly at about 0.5-0.6 of Φ_f , and Φ_f does not increase by adding more GF and reaches the maximum packing value (Φ_{fm}), as listed in Table 3.

Existence of a reaction between titanate coupling agents and glass was recognized, by FTIR measurement, however, it was assumed that the reactivity was weaker than that of silane coupling agents (4-6). Moreover, by DSC measurement, the reaction temperature of titanate (TA) and silane coupling agent (SA) with PVC were under 175°C and at about 120°C, respectively, which showed that the reactivity of TA with PVC was smaller than that of SA.

Figure 3 shows the SEM photographs of the machined surfaces for the composites. The GF particles are aligned as a layer, but some distortions of the arrangement are observed in the highly GF filled samples. The similar photographs were observed for all series. The photograph (a) UT-5 of the specimen untreated with coupling agents shows that the GF particles are drawn out because of no reactivity between PVC and GF. In the other photographs (b) TA-5 and (c) SA-5, it is observed that some fragments of PVC is adhered on the surfaces of the GF particles.

The maximum packing values (Φ_{fm}) of square or rectangle plates and disks should be 1.00 and 0.91, respectively, if the orientation of fillers are good. In the case, some distortion of GF and incomplete adhesion between GF and PVC matrix increase the voids and decrease the Φ_{fm} , consequently.

Figure 1

Relation between densities and filler concentration

Figure 2

Ternary phase diagram of three-phase composites of PVC, GF, and voids

Table 3

The maximum packing value

System	Φ_{fm}
UT	0.57
TB	0.62
TT	0.62
TA	0.68
SA	0.66

(a) UT-5

(b) TA-5

(c) SA-5

Figure 3

SEM photographs of machined surfaces of PVC-GF composites (magnification, 2000)

Dynamic mechanical properties

Figure 4 (a) and (b) show the temperature dependence of storage modulus E' and $\tan\delta$ observed at 110 Hz for the series TT and TA, respectively. The values of storage modulus in the specimens filled with GF particles are outstanding over the whole temperature range. On the other hand, the heights of α -peak of $\tan\delta$ maximum decrease in the specimens filled with GF particles.

Relative modulus, $E_r' = E_c'/E_m'$ (E_c' and E_m' are moduli of filled and unfilled samples, respectively), is plotted against $T-T_g$ for the series TT and TA samples in Figure 5 (a) and (b), respectively. The values of relative modulus in the glassy and rubbery states are remained nearly constant, except for the transition state. The similar behaviors were observed for the other series.

Relative modulus is plotted against the volume fraction of GF in the glassy state in Figure 6. The curves pass through a maximum at 0.45-0.55 of Φ_f . The maximum points of relative modulus are 2.2-2.4 which are smaller to compare with about 15 at $\Phi_f=0.49$ of epoxy resin-mica system (3). In the Figure 6, the curves calculated by using of Wu's and modified Halpin-Tsai's equations are also shown. Here, $1.85-1.93 \times 10^9 \text{ N/m}^2$ is used as the value of matrix dynamic modulus at $T = T_g - 60^\circ\text{C}$. Young's modulus of the E-glass is $7.26 \times 10^{10} \text{ N/m}^2$.

The effect of shapes of filler on elastic moduli has been investigated by Wu (7), who proposed the equation written as following relationship for the composite with randomly oriented disk-shaped particles, in order to simplify the calculation, using the Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.25$ for the matrix, filler, and composite:

$$E_r' = \frac{9 - 4\Phi_f + 4\Phi_f \cdot E_{gm}'}{9 - 5\Phi_f + 5(\Phi_f/E_{gm}')} \quad (1)$$

where $E_{gm}' = E_f'/E_m'$, in the case, $E_{gm}'=38$. In the case of the glassy state, the relative moduli of all PVC-GF series are very small and do not fit to Wu's theoretical prediction.

Figure 4

Temperature dependence of dynamic storage modulus E' and $\tan\delta$ of PVC-GF composites

Figure 5

Temperature dependence of the relative modulus

Figure 6

Dependence of the relative modulus on the volume fraction of GF at $T = T_g - 60^\circ\text{C}$

On the other hand, Halpin and Tsai (8-9) have proposed the theory to predict a lod type of reinforcement. A modified Halpin-Tsai equation, which was obtained by the method similar to that of Lewis and Nielsen's modification on the Kerner equation predicting a sphere type of reinforcement by introducing the maximum packing value (10), is as follows:

$$E_r' = \frac{1 + A \cdot B \cdot \Phi_f}{1 - B \cdot \Psi \cdot \Phi_f} \quad (2)$$

where

$$A = 2(AR)$$

$$B = (E_{gm}' - 1) / (E_{gm}' + A)$$

$$\Psi = 1 + \Phi_f(1 - \Phi_{fm}) / \Phi_{fm}^2.$$

The AR is the ratio of length to width of filler. In the case, AR equals to 1. As shown by the experimental data in Figure 6, the values of E_r' for all PVC-GF series at about $\Phi_f=0.2$ are near the modified Halpin-Tsai's equation. However, as the volume fraction of GF increases, the experimental data points of E_r' are found to be apart from the equation, for the reason that the voids in the specimens disturb the wetting between matrix and GF particles.

An evaluation of the effect of the treatment of titanate and silane coupling agents to storage modulus of the composites was made by calculating E_{gm}' by the modified Halpin-Tsai equation using various different values of the modulus of GF agreeing with the experimental data. Figure 7 shows E_{gm}' values agreed with the experimental data relating to volume fraction of GF. TA has larger contribution to the storage modulus comparing with the other titanates TB and TT, owing to the end amino groups acting as plasticizer. SA reacts with GF and PVC under the moulding temperature, while titanates react hardly with PVC. Therefore, PVC treated with SA has weaker fluidity and has poorer wettability to GF particles than that treated with titanates. The larger contribution of titanate coupling agents to the storage modulus than that of silane coupling agents might be owing to these facts.

Figure 7

Relationship between the ratio of modulus of GF to that of PVC calculated by equation (2) and the volume fraction of GF at $T = T_g - 60^\circ\text{C}$

REFERENCES

- 1 Price, H.L. and Nelson, J.B., "Phase Relationship in Three-Phase Composites Which Include a Void Phase," J. Compos. Mater., Vol.10, 1976, pp.314-318
- 2 Tanaka, K. and Adachi, K., "Dynamic Mechanical Properties of Poly(vinyl Chloride) Filled with Glass Powders. V. Glass Flake Series," Polymer Preprint, Japan, Vol.30, No.3, 1981, pp. 490
- 3 Iisaka, K. and Shibayama, K., "Effect of Orientation of Two-Dimensional Filler on Dynamic Mechanical Properties of Cured Epoxy Resin," J. Appl. Polym. Sci., Vol.20, 1976, pp, 813-823
- 4 For example; Arkles, B., "Tailoring Surfaces with Silanes," Chemtech, No.12, 1977, pp. 766-778
- 5 Ishida, H. and Koenig, J.L., for example; "Molecular Organization of the Coupling Agent Interphase of Fiber-Glass Reinforced Plastics," J. Polym. Sci., Polym. Phys. Ed., Vol.17, 1979, pp. 1807-1813
- 6 Adachi, K., Tanaka, K., and Ando, K., "FTIR Spectra of Glass Treated with Silane Coupling Agents," Preprint of 44th Meeting of Chem. Soc. Japan, Vol.1, 1981, pp. 144
- 7 Wu, Y.T., "The Effect of Inclusion Shape on the Elastic Moduli of a Two-Phase Material," Int. J. Solids Struct., Vol.2, 1966, pp. 1-8
- 8 Halpin, J.C., "Stiffness and Expansion Estimates for Oriented Short Composites," J. Compos. Mater., Vol.3, 1969, pp.732-734
- 9 Halpin, J.C. and Kardos, J.L., "Moduli of Crystalline Polymers Employing Composite Theory," J. Appl. Phys., Vol.43, pp. 2235-2241
- 10 Lewis, T.B. and Nielsen, L.E., "Dynamic Mechanical Properties of Particle-Filled Composites," J. Appl. Polym. Sci., Vol.14, 1970, pp. 1449-1471